

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

NARRATIVE TECHNIQUES IN THE TEXT INTERPRETATION

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Abstract

This article touches upon the significant aspect in text interpretation. The interpretation of English prose has its focus on a number of structural elements that construct the scheme for the discourse. These elements are used to produce certain effects; for instance, the type of the plot, the narrative voice, the narrative mode, methods of thought representation.

Keywords: homodiegetic; heterodiegetic; focalization; mimesis; diegesis; interior monologue; psychonarration; narrated monologue; stream-of-consciousness

To analyse a piece of prose is to comprehend its complex structural unity of means of expression and expressed tone, form and content. The systematic nature of all narrative techniques used in a text, their interrelation and interdependence, the consideration of all expressive means - all these are the factors that determine the completeness, depth and perception of the text and serve to reveal the thematic content of the literary text, and, consequently, help its adequate interpretation.

It is essential that students should formulate the main idea conveyed by the author (the main line of the thought, the author's message) at the initial stage of text interpretation. The next stage is to give a general definition of the text under study, following the structural elements.

While considering the length and events of prose, any narrative has one or more plot-lines. There are numerous single plot novels as well as multiple plot lines. The latter ones can have a main plot-line and several subplot-lines. The purpose of sub-plots is to contrast the main plot when, for example, there is the same chain of events in the similar sphere [1, pp 258-270]. The further distinction is between tightly-plotted and loosely-plotted narratives. In tightly-plotted texts everything happens for a reason and one event is the consequence of another. When each plot line is brought to a satisfactory ending, the narrative has a closed structure. For loosely-plotted narratives all the events or episodes are linked by a protagonist, whereas there is less emphasis on the causal connection between events. Such type of prose is specific with open-ended plots.

Narrative voices are defined by a person who tells a story. There is a classification of the technique as a homodiegetic narrator/ first-person narrative; a heterodiegetic narrator/ third-person narrative; and, occasionally, a second-person narrative. If the homodiegetic narrator is also the protagonist of the narrative, it is an autodiegetic narrator [2, pp 163-186].

One more distinction is between *telling* and *showing* or *an overt narrator* and *a covert narrator*. The overt narrator makes their judgements and evaluation, expresses their opinion openly. In case of the covert

narrator we know nothing about the speaker's own position. Sometimes a heterodiegetic narrator acquires the position of the omniscient narrator - the one who is able to tell us the thoughts and feelings of all the characters, though the story focuses on the point of view of one or two characters. Moreover, a homodiegetic or a heterodiegetic narrator can function as an unreliable narrator. The main reason for such transformation is to deliberately lead the reader to distrust and produce suspense. To the category of narrative voices we add the subtype of a heterodiegetic narrator - free indirect style - thoughts and feelings of a character expressed directly in the form of one or two affirmatives or rhetorical questions.

To make the classification complete we suggest students define the type of focalization that can function as perspective of the story. An external focaliser is a focaliser who is external to the story and who is thus often called narrator-focaliser because the focus of perception seems to be that of the narrator [3, pp 73-74]. The purpose of this type is to create a distance and to undermine the empathy with the protagonist. An internal focaliser is a, usually limited, focus of perception of a character in the story, and thus also called character-focaliser. Internal focalisation helps the readers to empathise with the character-focaliser.

Further classification deals with narrative modes. Narrative modes are the kinds of utterance through which a narrative is conveyed [4, pp 26-34]. For the text interpretation it is advisable to define four types of text presentation: mimesis/diegesis, report, description, and comment. Mimetic narrative mode is direct speech, whereas in diegetic one the speech is rendered indirectly. Report is the mode that informs the reader about events and actions in the story. Reports are frequently mingled with narrator comment. Description is a narrative mode that represents objects in space. It can be subdivided into three categories: description of place, of time, and of character. Notably, these elements are usually combined in narrative. In comment we find evaluations of the story's events and characters, general observations or judgements made by the narrator. Such evaluations can be more or less explicit.

Representation of thought/consciousness is considered the equally essential part of text interpretation. Three major methods of thought representation have been identified, depending on the level of noticeable narrator interference. They are: interior monologue, psychonarration, and narrated monologue or free indirect discourse [5, pp 12-17].

Interior monologue is intended to present a character's thoughts directly, imitating as much as possible the way this character might 'actually' have thought his thoughts. In other words, it is a longish passage of uninterrupted thoughts. It is a narrative technique, necessarily limited to verbal representation – that tries to reproduce non-orderly and associative patterns of thought. When other sensual perceptions are included, especially visual representations, we have the example of a psychological concept – stream of consciousness. Due to heated arguments around these two ways of representation, we have finally identified both of them as narrative techniques, with the focus on the distinctive feature of stream-of-consciousness: representation of one's thoughts that are not in fact orderly and wellformulated but more of a jumbled-up sequence of associations.

In *psychonarration* the heterodiegetic narrator remains in the foreground throughout, even adds some general observations not originating in the character. While we learn about the character's thoughts and feelings, we hear it entirely in the narrator's voice, syntax and vocabulary. The difference in effect is quite noticeable; the reader remains much more distant from the character's consciousness.

In *narrated monologue* the narrator refers to the character in third person and narrative past, the syntax becomes less formal (incomplete sentences, exclamations, ellipses). This technique can create immediacy but can also be used to create ironic distance [6, pp 69-75].

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